

USE SOME METHODS IN ENGLISH

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***Abstract:** The article also tells about the ways of a foreign language acquisition, the secondary role of grammar and the priority of communicative competence. All these helps the learners to make the process of learning more comprehensible.*

***Key words:** enhance, proficiently, challenge, final completion, grammar-translation method, bilingual translation, pattern.*

Teaching involves a continuous analysis of one's own work, the experiences of other teachers and the search for new means to improve teaching. When teaching a foreign language a teacher must think about the specific qualities offered to students of a certain mother tongue. That means that the methodology of teaching English has to take into account the problems posed by the English language for the students who will learn it. The methodology of teaching English stands in relation with several challenges or problems: 1. What to teach? That means the amount of knowledge, skills and habits that students have to obtain within the process of learning the language. 2. What are the aims of teaching? When a teacher is sure of the aim of teaching, he/she will have the easiness of reaching the intended goal. 3. How to teach? In this case one can call to mind the principles upon which teaching of English is based, the means, methods, fashion and tactics used in teaching in order to achieve the required final completion [1]. Modern foreign languages were studied in the grammar-based format the same way Latin had been taught previously. This method

dominated foreign language studies for over 300 years. According to the grammar-translation method the language is a synthesis of words arranged in sentences according to different rules of different languages. Students were supposed to learn words and grammatical rules and construct sentences based on these. The words were grouped in lists and the rules were memorized in a strict order. This system of learning a language was very rigid. Learning in this way students were not able to embrace the variety and richness of the spoken language. New paths in teaching a foreign language were introduced along the centuries to come. Jean Joseph Jacotot a professor who taught French introduced the procedure of bilingual texts. In his classes he used to read twice, aloud and slowly a certain text which was already translated in French. The students would follow the reading in bilingual translation. The students then were requested to divide up the text in smaller parts, then in sentences and in words and in the end in letters and sounds. To him this was the natural pattern to teach a foreign language. But it was Francois Gouin, a professor of Latin who lived in France in the nineteenth century, who pointed to the insufficiencies of the teaching methods of his time. The story says that he went to Germany to study German and after several trials of memorizing, first verbs and words and then a whole book of conversations. However, he was not able to understand or converse in German at all, although he studied very hard. He pointed out that in the teaching of foreign languages one must start with the auditory perception [2]. That means the principal organ for learning is the ear and not the eye. So for the acquisition of a foreign language the best means is that of hearing and not reading. People always express themselves in sentences so the basis in the study of a language cannot be the isolated word. In the second half of the 19th century polemics concerning the teaching of a foreign

language gave birth to the Reform Movement, which comprised ideas of reforming the old-school systems. The teaching of English as a second language represented a main impetus. In the meantime, searching for new paths continued. Polemics concerning the teaching of foreign languages went hand in hand with the idea of reforming the old school systems. In classes mother tongue began to be excluded almost entirely when teaching of English. Correct pronunciation was very important and grammar rules were secondary. Grammar was achieved by practice. The students were given texts and not unconnected sentences to prove certain grammatical rules. During the whole 20th century new theories appeared. Especially the period from second half of the 20th century, from the 50's to 80's has been known as the Age of Methods. Numerous methods in Europe and the USA came forth. They were acknowledged as Silent Way, Total Physical Response, Suggestopedia, The Natural Approach, Community Language Learning, and Audio Lingual Approach. Concerning teaching methods, I believe that a variety of approaches makes up the most successful practice, it assists to maintain the whole attention of the students present in class, it encourages them and offers an attractive atmosphere and diminishes anxiety, shyness, etc. In the end I would like to add the following fact: not all students share the same desire for studying a foreign language and it is sometimes a bit too hard for a teacher to teach a class even if he/she is very enthusiastic when teaching the lesson. It has happened to me, it has happened to others [3].

List of used literature:

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2. Tamura E., Naganuma S. Food in History. Eihosha, 2006.

3. Asher James. Brainswitching, A skill for the 21st Century Sky Oaks Productions. Inc. Los Gatos. California, 1988.